

References

1. K. N. JOHRI and H. C. MEHRA, *Sep. Sci.*, 1976, **11**, 171.
2. A. L. J. RAO and SURINDER, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1973, **267**, 46.
3. K. N. JOHRI and H. C. MEHRA, *Chromatographia*, 1976, **8**, 244.
4. R. K. UPADHYAY and A. P. TIWARI, *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 1980, **3**, 911.
5. R. K. UPADHYAY, V. KUMARI and V. P. SINGH, *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 1982, **5**, 1141.
6. R. K. UPADHYAY, V. KUMARI and V. P. SINGH, *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 1983, **6**, 155.
7. R. K. UPADHYAY and V. P. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1164; 1977, **54**, 475.
8. R. K. UPADHYAY, K. BHATI and A. K. BAJPAI, *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 1984, **7**, 2831.

[1,3]Dioxolo[4,5-g]pyrimido[1,2-a][3,1]benzothiazin-6-one

H. K. GAKHAR*, PUNAM SACHDEV

and

SHASHI BHUSHAN GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University,
Chandigarh-160 014

Manuscript received 4 December 1984,
accepted 11 September 1985

THE syntheses of some 1,3-dioxolo[4,5-g]pyrimido[1,2-a][3,1]benzothiazines with different alkyl-substituted-amino groups at 6-position has already been reported¹ from this laboratory. A review of literature reveals that noteworthy results are obtained by making structural variations in a section of the molecule. With this aim in mind, the synthesis of 1,3,3-trimethyl-3*H*,6*H*-[1,3]dioxolo[4,5-g]pyrimido[1,2-a][3,1]benzothiazine with a keto group at 6-position (6) has been undertaken.

It has been achieved by the condensation of methyl-6-aminopiperonylate (1) with 2-methyl-2-isothiocyanopentan-4-one (2). Isothiocyanates as well as the ketones are known to react with amines but the former are more reactive compared to the latter. Thus first step would lead to the formation of thiourea derivative, methyl-6-[[[(1,1-dimethyl-3-oxobutyl)amino]thioxomethyl]amino]-1,3-benzodioxole-5-carboxylate (3) which could give rise to 4 or 5 or a mixture of both depending upon the mode of cyclisation. However, even by careful experiments, only one product could be isolated as evident by tlc which has been assigned structure methyl-6[3,4-dihydro-4,4,6-trimethyl-2-thioxo-1(2*H*)pyrimidinyl]-1,3-benzodioxole-5-carboxylate (4) on the basis of ir spectra which gave a characteristic band at 1235 cm⁻¹ due to C=S. The C=O of the conjugated ester and N-H bands appeared at 1700 and 3150 cm⁻¹, respectively. Pmr spectra of 4 in CDCl₃ showed three singlets of three proton intensity each at δ 1.40, 1.46 and 1.57; the first two assignable to protons of the gem dimethyl groups and the last one

to three allylic protons (H_βC=C=CH-). Besides, it exhibited two more singlets, one of two proton intensity and the other of three proton intensity at δ 6.16 and 3.90 which are attributed to two methylenedioxy protons (-OCH₂O-) and two proton of the ester (-CO-OCH₃), respectively. It also exhibited two singlets of one proton intensity each at 4.85 and 6.86, the former due to one vinylic proton (C=CH-) and the latter due to single proton attached to nitrogen (NH exchangeable with D₂O). Two aromatic protons C₄-H and C₇-H appeared as two sharp singlets at δ 7.53 and 6.80, respectively. Moreover, the compound was found to be soluble in 10% sodium hydroxide solution which further supported the structure 4.

This has further been confirmed by preparing the isomeric compound 5 by an unambiguous route involving the condensation of 1 with 2-mercapto-4,4,6-trimethyl-1*H*,4*H*-(1,3)thiazine (8). The compound 5 thus formed, besides other signals, gave a singlet of three proton intensity at δ 3.86 assignable to ester but differed from the compound prepared by the condensation of 1 and 2 in m.p. and R_f value, and did not give any ir band around 1235 cm⁻¹, thus lending further support to structure 4. Moreover 5 was insoluble in 10% sodium hydroxide solution, which further confirmed structural assignment (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

4 on treatment with sodium ethoxide gave 6. The pmr spectrum of 6 in CDCl₃ showed the absence of a three proton singlet at δ 3.90 due to ester (-CO-OCH₃) and a singlet at 6.86 due to N-H. The protons of two gem dimethyl groups were observed as singlets of three proton intensity each at δ 1.23 and 1.33. There allylic protons (CH_β-C=CH-) appeared as a singlet at δ 1.53 and the lone vinylic proton (-C=CH-) appeared as a broad singlet at δ 5.37. Besides, it also showed one more singlet (2*H*) at δ 6.13 due to two methyl-

enedioxy protons. Two aromatic protons, C_7-H and $C_{11}-H$ appeared as two sharp singlets at δ 7.46 and 7.33, respectively.

It is quite interesting that 4 on treatment with ethanolic hydrochloric acid gas underwent retrogression to give rise to 1 and 2. The retrogression could be represented as in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

Reagents: 1, OH^- , ketonisation.

Attempts to cyclise 5 to get 7 by refluxing in ethanol for 15 h did not materialise. However, efforts are on way to cyclise 5 by using different catalysts.

Experimental

Compounds were routinely checked for their homogeneity by tlc on silica gel G. Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 90MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

Methyl-6-[3,4-dihydro-4,4,6-trimethyl-2-thioxo-1-(2H)pyrimidinyl]-1,3-benzodioxole-5-carboxylate (4):

Method A: Methyl-6-aminopiperonylate⁸ (1; 1.95 g, 0.01 mol) and 2-methyl-2-isothiocyanopentan-4-one⁹ (2; 1.57 g, 0.01 mol) were mixed together and heated on a steam-bath. Initially the contents became mobile but as the reaction proceeded the mass became solid. After heating it for 3 h, the product was cooled and crystallised from ethanol (1.84 g, 55%), m.p. 192° (Found: C, 57.28; H, 5.47; N, 8.21. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2O_4S$ requires C, 57.49; H, 5.39; N, 8.38%).

Method B: To a solution of 1 (0.195 g, 0.001 mol) in ethanol (5 ml) was added 2 (0.16 g, 0.0011 mol). After keeping for 5 days at room temperature (25-30°), the compound separated was filtered under suction and crystallised from ethanol (48%), m.p. 192°. It was found to be the intermediate 4 identical in all respect with the compound obtained by Method A.

1,3,3-Trimethyl-3H,6H-[1,3]dioxolo[4,5-g]pyrimido[1,2-a][3,1]benzothiazin-6-one (6): A solution of 4 (3.34 g, 0.01 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml) was added dropwise to freshly prepared sodium ethoxide in the same solvent (20 ml) with continuous stirring at room temperature. The turbidity increased as the addition progressed. After the completion of addition, the contents were refluxed over a steam-bath for 8 h. Benzene was distilled off and the residue was dissolved in water and filtered. The filtrate on

acidification with acetic acid furnished the product 6 which was collected under suction, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (2.26 g, 75%), m.p. 227° (Found: C, 59.78; H, 4.43; N, 9.39. $C_{18}H_{14}N_2O_8S$ requires C, 59.60; H, 4.64; N, 9.27%).

Methyl-6-[(4,4,6-trimethyl-4H-1,3-thiazin-2-yl)amino]-1,3-benzodioxole-5-carboxylate (5): A mixture of 1 (0.195 g, 0.001 mol) and 2-mercapto-4,4,6-trimethyl-1H,4H(1,3) thiazine⁴ (8; 0.173 g, 0.001 mol) was heated on an oil-bath at 100° for 8 h and then the temperature was raised to 120° for 3 h. At this temperature the evolution of H_2S practically ceased. After cooling, the product was crystallised from carbon tetrachloride, yield (0.2 g, 60%), m.p. 95-6° (Found: C, 57.24; H, 5.54; N, 8.52. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2O_4S$ requires C, 57.49; H, 5.39; N, 8.38%). ν_{max} 3120 (NH) and 1665 cm^{-1} ($-CO-O-CH_3$); δ ($CDCl_3$) 8.56 (1H, bs, NH exchangeable with D_2O), 7.30 (1H, s, C_4-H Ar), 6.21 (1H, s, C_7-H Ar), 5.93 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 5.53 (1H, s, $-CH=$), 3.86 (3H, s, $COOCH_3$), 1.93 (3H, s, $=C-CH_3$), 1.43 (6H, s, $=C(CH_3)_2$).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. Kurt L. Loening, Nomenclature Director, Chemical Abstracts Service, U.S.A., for nomenclature and the authorities of Panjab University, Chandigarh, for the award of Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (S.B.G.).

References

1. H. K. GAKHAR, J. S. MULTANI and K. S. NARANG, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 698.
2. E. ORTLY and A. PICTET, *Chem. Ber.*, 1910, 43, 1936.
3. R. A. MATHES, F. D. STEWART and F. SWEDISH, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1452.
4. J. E. JANSSEN and R. A. MATHES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 5431.

Chemical Constituents of *Allanthus grandis* Prain

H. N. KHASTGIR and B. P. PRADHAN

Department of Chemistry, University of North Bengal,
P. O. North Bengal University, Darjeeling-734 430

D. R. MISRA

Ordinance Factory, Government of India, Calcutta

B. SAHA

Department of Botany, University of Columbia,
Vancouver, B. C., Canada

and

A. NATH

Department of Chemistry, St. Joseph's College, Darjeeling

Manuscript received 19 July 1983, accepted 11 September 1985

THE isolation and characterisation of two quassinoids, viz. 6 α -tigloyloxychaparrin and 6 α -tigloyloxychaparrinone from the bark of *Allanthus grandis* Prain have been reported earlier¹. A complete report on the chemical constituents of the same